

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

PTN (pleiotrophin)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

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TARGET SOURCE & HYPOTHESIS

Why was the target selected? This target is found within a TMT proteomics network module that was highly correlated with cognition. This module (Module 42) contains several novel AD targets, including SMOC1 and SFRP1.

TREAT-AD Target Risk Score: 3.16 (rank #4001, 84th percentile)

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics and genetics evidence. The Target Risk Score represents the gene target's general relevance to Alzheimer's Disease, and is the sum of the target's Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Target Risk Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being evidence of the strongest association with AD. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate these scores is available [here](#). This score was taken from Agora, Data Version syn13363290-v62.

The TREAT-AD Target Risk Score for this target is 3.16 out of 5 (rank #4001, 84th percentile). The individual score components include 1.3 of 3 for genetics, and 1.86 out of 2 for genomics. The meta-analysis of proteomic and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of PTN protein is significantly increased while the expression of PTN RNA is significantly decreased in brains from patients with AD.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (biodomains). These biological domains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biological domains via GO term annotations. PTN is annotated to GO terms from 6 different biodomains, but primarily to terms from the Synapse, Myelination, and Immune Response biological domains.

Overall	rank	pctl	GeneticsScore	OmicsScore
3.162	4001	83.98	1.298	1.864

Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell expression data from the Seattle Alzheimer's Disease Brain Cell Atlas (SEA-AD). The distribution of expression values for all genes found in each broad cell type are displayed as violins. The expression of the target in subtypes within each broad class is shown as a point. Blue points show the summary expression of cells from individuals with no dementia, while red points show summary metrics of cells from dementia patients. Open

circles reflect low confidence measures of expression. The expression of PTN is confidently detected in vascular and leptomeningeal cells (VLMC), astrocytes, oligodendrocyte precursor cells (OPC), oligodendrocytes, and some inhibitory neuron sub-types within this dataset.

SUMMARY OF PROJECT

Pleiotrophin is a heparin binding growth factor that appears to play diversity roles in neurology, with evidence supporting a pro-synaptic neuronal survival promoting role, and countering evidence suggesting a role in augmenting microglial proliferation and neuroinflammatory response to toxic cytokines (evidence discussed below). The goal of this TEP is to provide the scientific community with high quality resources that may help validate, differentiate, and further investigate these roles of PTN in AD. The contents of this TEP include bioinformatic analysis, protein structural information and purified protein, and validated antibodies for PTN investigations. We hope these resources facilitate the efficiency and accuracy of future work in the field.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

Pleiotrophin (PTN) is a heparin binding growth factor involved in numerous processes in the brain (1). There is a small but evolving literature discussing the role of PTN in synaptic biology, which preliminary studies support PTN involvement in synapse extension and neurite development (2–4). One mechanism involves Triad repression of PTN ubiquitination, leading to increased synaptic growth (2). Interestingly, there is more literature about PTN regulation in addiction and recovery, supporting a role for neurite regrowth in this context (4,5), countering the toxicity of drugs of abuse. The promotion of neuronal survival in cells exposed to cytotoxic drugs, such as amphetamine and cocaine (5), makes it an interesting target to explore in Alzheimer’s disease (AD). Building upon the studies showing synapto-protective effects of PTN and a general promotion of neuronal survival, there is some data suggesting that PTN also promotes remyelination after neuronal injury through the repression of protein tyrosine phosphatase receptor type Z (6). Beyond the trophic effects within neuronal systems, PTN also appears to regulate microglial activity as well, as mice over-expressing a PTN transgene demonstrate elevated microglial inflammatory response to LPS treatment (7,8), potentially implicating a multitude of dichotomous role for PTN in different brain cell types. Accordingly, while PTN potentiates microglial inflammatory response, it also appears to decrease astrocytic gliosis (9), showing that PTN has a diversity of roles even within glial lineages. PTN is also implicated in cancer studies, in which it promotes glioma proliferation (10–12), which appears to be a general function of PTN on glial lines, as PTN promotes glial proliferation through activation of the ERK/MAPK pathway (8). These roles suggest counter-regulatory mechanisms involved in neurodegenerative process—a role which is at least weakly supported by the up-regulation of PTN in neurodegeneration (13). While there is little data supporting a specific role for PTN in AD, it does appear capable of regulating the fundamental biological mechanisms that either promote neuronal survival and synaptic viability, or activation of microglial pro-inflammatory effects, or perhaps both at different times or under different conditions in the disease sequelae.

RESULTS – THE TEP

Validated Antibodies & Generic Knockout Cell Lines

The YCharOS Antibody Characterization Report guides researchers to select the most appropriate antibodies for PTN. The YCharOS antibody characterization pipeline uses knockout (KO) cells to perform head-to-head comparisons of available commercial antibodies for PTN by immunoblot (Western blot), immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence. The cell line background was chosen based on the adequate expression of the target protein.

[YCharOS Pleiotrophin antibody characterization report](#)

Protein constructs and expression methods: proteins purified

1. PTNA-c200: Human full-length PTN (E33-E168). Contains an ectopic N-terminal secretion signal and a C-terminal His6 tag. Protein produced in Expi293F cells.

See **Additional information (section 1)** with details of plasmid expression constructs and purification procedures.

Cell type specific expression:

Using anti-human PTN antibody ab79411 as appears in the [YCharOS Pleiotrophin Antibody Characterization Report](#), PTN expression was easily detected in human iPSC-derived neurons but minimally detected in human iPSC-derived astrocytes and microglia (Fig. 1). See **Additional Information** for cell line information, iPSC differentiation protocols, and Western blot conditions.

Figure 1. Expression of PTN in whole cell lysates (top) and media (bottom) across neurons (N), astrocytes (A), and microglia (M) derived from iPSC cell lines WTC11 (left) and F033K (right). Independent samples (n=2) were run in adjacent lanes.

Biological probe discovery:

- 1) Immunodepletion of secreted protein in medium :** PTN was immunoprecipitated from media conditioned with WTC11-derived neurons. PTN was measured in eluate following immunoprecipitation by Western blot, and unbound PTN was detected in flowthrough by Western blot (Fig. 2). See **Additional Information** for experimental information on immunoprecipitation and Western blotting.

Figure 2. Immunoprecipitation (IP) of PTN using validated antibody ab79411 from iPSC-derived F033K neuron conditioned media. Western blot of eluted PTN (top) and unbound PTN in flowthrough (bottom) from media samples, n=3 technical replicates of single sample collection loaded in three adjacent lanes.

2) **Cell-based assays following immunodepletion:** To understand the impact of modulating PTN on cell function, we performed a small panel of assays on cells treated with anti-PTN antibody. WTC11 iPSC-derived neurons were treated with anti-PTN before measuring A β 40 and A β 42 in conditioned media (Fig. 3). iPSC-derived astrocytes were treated with anti-PTN before measuring IL-6 in conditioned media (Fig. 4). Treatment with anti-PTN slightly decreased A β 42 and A β 40 levels without affecting the A β 42:A β 40 ratio in iPSC-neurons and more than doubled IL-6 levels in iPSC-astrocytes. See **Additional Information** for experimental information.

Figure 3. Immunodepletion of PTN from iPSC derived neurons by treatment with anti-PTN antibody. A β 40 and A β 42 levels in WTC11 neuron conditioned media when treated with anti-PTN antibody or IgG as measured by ELISA, n=3 independent experiments . ***p<0.001, ****p <0.0001, and ns= p>0.05.

Figure 4. Immunodepletion of PTN from iPSC derived astrocytes by treatment with anti-PTN antibody. IL-6 levels in WTC11 astrocyte conditioned media when treated with anti-PTN antibody or IgG as measured by ELISA, n=2 independent experiments *p<0.05.

3) Cell-based assays following treatment with recombinant protein: To understand the impact of modulating PTN on cell function, we performed a small panel of assays on cells treated with recombinant PTN. WTC11 iPSC-derived astrocytes were treated with recombinant PTN before measuring cell viability (Fig. 5A), cytotoxicity (Fig. 5B), and mitochondrial function (Fig.5C). Treatment with recombinant PTN protein did not have any toxic effects on the astrocytes as indicated by the AlamarBlue and LDH experiments. Recombinant PTN protein treatment did not have any significant effect on mitochondrial function. See **Additional Information** for experimental details.

Figure 5. Activity of WTC11 iPSC-derived astrocytes following PTN protein treatment. A) AlamarBlue viability assay B) LDH cytotoxicity assay C) Mitotracker assay, n=3 independent experiments, *p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p<0.001. BSA serves as control.

CONCLUSION

The tools presented here provide a foundation for further biological investigation of the role of PTN1 in AD.

FUNDING INFORMATION

The work performed by the Emory-Sage-SGC TREAT-AD Center has been funded by the National Institute on Aging through grant U54 AG065187.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Materials and Methods

Protein expression constructs and protein purification

All relevant plasmids are available on addgene: [TREAT-AD plasmid collection](#)

1. **PTNA-c200**: Human full-length PTN (E33-E168). Contains an ectopic N-terminal secretion signal and a C-terminal Avi-His6 tag. Protein produced in Expi293F cells.

Construct ID	PTNA-c200
Parental vector	pHL-avitag3
Tag	C-terminal His6
Protein mass (with tag and secretion signal)	22002.5 Da
Extinction Coefficient (M⁻¹ cm⁻¹)	28990
Protein sequence (with tag)	MGILPSPGMPALLSLVSLLSVLLMGCVAETGGKKEKPEKKVKKSDCGEWQWSVCV PTSGDCGLGTREGTRTGAECKQTMKTQRCKIPCNWKKQFGAECKYQFQAWGEC DLNTALKTRTGSALKRALHNAECQKTVTISKPCGKLTKPKPQAESKKKKKEGKKQEKM LDGTGGSGGSLNDIFEAQKIEWHEGRTKHHHHHH

Purified Protein	
Heparin affinity chromatography: PTNA-c200 (with tag)	<p>Two SDS-PAGE gels showing protein purification. The left gel is labeled 'Ni IMAC' and the right gel is labeled 'Heparin affinity'. Both gels have molecular weight markers on the left ranging from 10 to 250 kDa. In both gels, a prominent band is visible at approximately 25 kDa, indicating the presence of the PTNA-c200 protein.</p>

Intact Mass Deconvolution: PTNA-c200 (with tag)	
Observed Mass:	19926.4 Da
Protein yield:	2mg/L of culture

Expression and Purification Protocol	
Expression host	<i>Mammalian</i> : Expi293F cells (Thermo Fisher Scientific)
Expression medium	FreeStyle 293 Expression Medium (Thermo Fisher Scientific)
Plasmid purification	Transform the construct into the <i>E. coli</i> strain MACH1. Plate on LB-agar plates containing ampicillin (100 µg/ml). Inoculate 5 ml LB broth containing ampicillin (100 µg/ml) with a single colony and grow 6h at 37°C with shaking. Inoculate 800 ml LB broth containing the same antibiotic with 2 ml of starter culture and grow overnight at 37°C with shaking. Split culture into 4 and perform MaxiPrep (Qiagen) with 4 columns according to manufacturer’s instructions. Add 0.7 volumes of isopropanol to precipitate the plasmid. Spin (17000g, 30 min, 4°C) and wash pellet with 70% ethanol. Resuspend plasmid with sterile TE buffer under sterile conditions. Yield is typically 2 mg of plasmid.
Transfection	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Split Expi293F cells to 1x10⁶ cells/ml in 1L FreeStyle 293 Expression Medium. Incubate for 24 h until cells are approximately 2x10⁶ cells/ml (37°C, 150 rpm, 8% CO₂, 75% rh). 2. Add plasmid to 20mL of pre-warmed Opti-MEM at 0.5 µg/ml final concentration. 3. Add linear PEI (1 mg/ml sterile stock) to another 20mL of pre-warmed Opti-MEM at 3 µg/ml final concentration. 4. Add the mixture from Step 3 to the one in Step 2 and incubate at room temperature for 30 min. 5. Add the plasmid/PEI mixture slowly to the cells. 6. Add sodium butyrate (1 M sterile stock) to 12 mM final concentration. 7. Incubate cells at 30°C (8%CO₂/75% rh) with shaking at 150 rpm.

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. Harvest cell culture supernatant at 5 days post transfection (900g, 20 min, 4°C). 9. Filter supernatant through 0.2 µm filter.
Purification buffers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ni IMAC W10 buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 200 mM NaCl, 10 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol 2. Ni IMAC W25 buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 200 mM NaCl, 25 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol 3. Ni IMAC elution buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 200 mM NaCl, 250 mM imidazole, 2% glycerol 4. Heparin W1 buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 200 mM NaCl, 2% glycerol 5. Heparin W2 buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 2% glycerol 6. Heparin elution buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 1.5 M NaCl, 1% glycerol 7. Ni-sepharose beads, equilibrated in Ni IMAC W10 buffer. 8. Hi-Trap Heparin HP Column (Cytiva), equilibrated in Heparin W1 buffer.
Purification step 1: IMAC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Add imidazole to filtered supernatant to 10 mM final concentration. 2. Add a total of 2.5 ml equilibrated Ni-sepharose beads to the cell supernatant, split into 50-ml falcon tubes. Mix by rotation for 1 hr in a cold room. 3. Spin beads/supernatant slurry (700g, 5 min, 4°C). Decant supernatant and wash beads with 100 ml W10 buffer. Repeat wash with 50 ml W10. Spin again and transfer beads to gravity column in a cold room. 4. Wash column with 25 ml W25. 5. Elute protein with 1x 10 ml elution buffer, followed by 2x5 ml elution buffer. Analyse the EB fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using the Bradford assay.
Purification step 2: Heparin affinity chromatography	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Apply EB fractions containing the protein, using a syringe 'drop to drop' onto the column. 2. Wash the column with 10 ml of W1, followed by 10 ml of W2. 3. Elute protein with 3x 2ml heparin elution buffer. 4. Analyse the EB fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using UV spectroscopy. 5. Snap-freeze aliquots in thin-walled PCR tubes in liquid N₂, and store at -80°C.

Cell line information

The familial Alzheimer's disease (fAD) iPSC line (F033K) was previously generated from fibroblasts of a patient carrying the APP V717I (London) mutation (14). The well-characterized WTC11 iPSC line (15) and the F033K line were cultured in mTeSR1 medium (STEMCELL Technologies; Cat. No. 85850) on cell culture treated dishes coated with Geltrex LDEV-Free Reduced Growth Factor Basement Membrane Matrix (Gibco/Thermo Fisher Scientific; Cat. No. A1413201) diluted 1:100 in DMEM/F-12 (Gibco/Thermo Fisher Scientific; Cat. No. 11320033). Briefly, mTeSR1 was replaced every other day or every day once 50% confluent. When 80-90% confluent, cells were passaged, which entailed the following: aspirating media, washing with DPBS, incubating with ReLeSR (STEMCELL Technologies; Cat. No. 100-0484) at RT for 3 minutes, aspirating ReLeSR, and incubating at 37°C for 10 minutes, resuspending in mTeSR1 supplemented with 10nM Y-27632 dihydrochloride ROCK inhibitor (Tocris; Cat. No. 125410), counting, and plating onto Matrigel-coated plates at desired number.

iPSC differentiation protocols

Astrocytes: Human iPSC-derived astrocytes (iAs) were generated as previously described (16). Briefly, iPSCs were plated on Matrigel-coated 6-well plates and infected with rtTA, SOX9, and NFIB lentivirus. On Day 0, medium was replaced with fresh mTeSR-1 medium containing 2.5 µg/mL doxycycline. From Day 1-7, iAs were cultured in expansion medium (DMEM/F12, 10% FBS, 1% N2, 1.25 µg/mL puromycin, 200 µg/mL Hygromycin) and gradually transitioned to FGF medium (Neurobasal, 2% B27, 1% NEAA, 1% GlutaMax, 1% FBS, 8 ng/mL FGF, 5 ng/mL CNTF, 10 ng/mL BMP4, 200 µg/mL Hygromycin) by Day 7. On Day 7, iAs were dissociated using Accutase for 10 minutes, and replated on Matrigel-coated 6-well plates in FGF medium. From Day 9, FGF medium was changed to Maturation medium (1:1 DMEM/F12 and Neurobasal, 1% N2, 1% Na Pyruvate, 10 µg/µL NAC, 10 µg/µL hbEGF, 10 ng/mL CNTF, 10 ng/mL BMP4, 500 µg/mL cAMP) and half of the medium was changed every 2 to 3 days.

Neurons: Human iPSC-derived neurons (iNs) were generated as previously described (17). Briefly, iPSCs were plated on Matrigel-coated 6-well plates and infected with rtTA and NGN2 lentivirus. On Day 0, medium was replaced with fresh mTeSR-1 medium containing 2.5 µg/mL doxycycline. From Day 1-3, iNs were cultured in K2B medium (KO DMEM, 15% KSR, 1% NEAA, 0.1% BME, 1% GlutaMax, 2 µg/ml doxycycline) and gradually transitioned to N2B medium (DMEM/F12, 1% GlutaMax, 1.5% dextrose, 1% N2, 2 µg/ml doxycycline, 1 µg/mL puromycin) by Day 3. On Day 4, iNs were dissociated using Accutase for 5 minutes, and replated on Matrigel-coated 6-well plates in NBM medium (Neurobasal, 1% GlutaMax, 1.5% dextrose, 0.5% NEAA, 2% B27, 10 ng/ml BDNF, 10 ng/ml GDNF, 10 ng/ml CNTF, 2 µg/ml doxycycline, 1µg/mL puromycin) and half of the medium was changed every 2 to 3 days.

Microglia: Human iPSC-derived microglia-like cells (iMGL) were generated by first differentiating human iPSCs into hematopoietic progenitor cells using the STEMdiff Hematopoietic Kit (STEMCELL Technologies; Cat. No. 05310) per manufacturer's instructions. Then, hematopoietic progenitor cells were differentiated into microglia using the STEMdiff Microglia Differentiation Kit (STEMCELL Technologies; Cat. No. 100-0019) and matured using STEMdiff Microglia Maturation Kit (STEMCELL Technologies; Cat. No. 100-0020) following the manufacturer's instructions.

Western blotting

Media were collected and spun at 5000 X g for 10 min. The supernatants were stored at -80°C. For Western blotting, 1/3 volume of 4x Laemmli protein sample buffer (BioRad, 1610747) was added to culture media. After boiling at 98°C for 5 min. For cell lysate collection, after removing media, cells were washed with PBS twice and collected in PBS with a cell scraper. Cells were spun at 3000 rpm for 5 min, and the supernatants were discarded. Cells were lysed in NP-40 buffer (1% nonidet P-40, 20 mM Tris (PH 7.4), 137 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol) with protease inhibitor (Sigma, P8340) and phosphatase inhibitor (Sigma, P5726 and P0044). 1/3 volume of 4x Laemmli protein sample buffer (BioRad, #1610747) was added to lysate and samples were boiled at 98°C for 5 min. For Western blotting, cell culture media and lysates were separated on 12.5% Tris-glycine SDS-polyacrylamide gels. Proteins were transferred to 0.2 µm nitrocellulose membrane (BioRad, 1620112). The membrane was blocked with 5% non-fat milk for 1 hr and incubated with PTN antibody (Abcam, ab79411) with 1:1000 dilution in TBST containing 3% BSA at 4°C overnight with gentle rocking. The membrane was washed with TBST for 10 mins three times and then incubated with the secondary antibody (Jackson ImmunoResearch Laboratories, #111-035-003) at 1:5000 at room temperature for 1 hr. After washing with TBST for 10 mins three times, images were taken with the ChemiDoc Imaging System (BioRad, 12003153).

Immunoprecipitation

Cell culture media were collected as described above for Western blotting. PTN antibody (Abcam, ab79411) was added to media (0.75 µg/ml) and incubated at 4°C overnight with gentle rocking. Protein A/G beads (Santa Cruz, sc-2003) were prewashed with PBS twice and resuspended with lysis buffer after final wash. 30 µl slurry of resuspended beads were added to media which were incubated with the antibody. After two hours incubation at 4°C, beads were pelleted by centrifugation at 3,000 rpm (approximately 1,000xg) for 30 seconds at 4°C. The supernatants were collected to serve as flowthrough. Beads were washed with PBS 3 times. 30-50 µl 2x Laemmli sample buffer (BioRad, 1610737) was added to the beads pellet. After boiling for 5 minutes, samples can be stored at -20°C for Western blotting.

Immunodepletion in cell media

PTN antibody (Abcam, ab79411) was added to media (0.75 µg/ml) with iPSC derived cells. The cells were further cultured for 3 days at 37°C in humidified conditions with 5% CO₂. Cell culture media were collected as described above for Western blotting. Prewashed protein A/G beads were added to media and incubated at 4°C for two hours. The following steps are the same as immunoprecipitation for cell media described above.

Protein treatment of cells

iPSC-derived astrocytes were cultured on 96-well plates. Cells were treated with PTN protein (purified in house, see methods above) in 100 µl media on day 14 for 24 hours.

Measurement of Aβ and IL-6

Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) kits specific for human Aβ₄₀ and Aβ₄₂ (Invitrogen: #KHB3482 and #KHB3441) and IL-6 (R&D Systems: #QK206) were used to quantify Aβ species and IL-6 according to the manufacturer's instructions. Results were expressed as percentages of the isotype control. The means from duplicate measurements are presented.

AlamarBlue viability assay

20 µl CellTiter-Blue reagent (Promega, #G8088) was added to each well of a 96-well plate. After incubating for 4 hours at 37°C, Fluorescence Intensity (FI), which corresponds to the number of living cells, was measured with PHERAstar FSX (BMG Labtech) plate reader (Ex. 560nm and Em. 590nm). Wells containing medium only were used to determine background signal.

LDH cytotoxicity assay

Cytotoxicity assay was performed using kit (Promega, J2380). Cell culture medium was diluted 20 fold with LDH storage buffer (200mM Tris-HCl (pH 7.3), 10% Glycerol, 1% BSA). 50 µl diluted culture medium was mixed with 50 µl LDH detection reagent in a 96-well opaque-walled, non-transparent assay plate with opaque bottom. After 60 minutes incubation at room temperature, luminescence signal was measured with EnVision 2103 Multilabel plate Reader (PerkinElmer).

Mitotracker assay

To stain mitochondria, mitochondrial membrane potential indicator, TMRM (ThermoFisher, #I34361), was diluted in culture medium containing the nuclear indicator Hoechst 33342. 5 µl staining solution was added to each well to final concentration of 100 nM TMRM and 10 µg/ml Hoechst 33342. After 30 minutes incubation at 37°C, cells were imaged with ImageXpress® Micro (Molecular Devices), and the fluorescence intensity of the cells was quantified with MetaXpress 6. Carbonyl cyanide-p-trifluoromethoxyphenylhydrazone (FCCP) was used as positive control at 100 µM. 30 minutes before adding staining solution, FCCP was added to cells at final concentration of 100 µM.

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